

Increasing Village Economic Independence through Assistance in Traditional Herb Product Innovation

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ABSTRACT

Increasing village economic independence through assistance in traditional herb product innovation is carried out with the village community. This activity is a National Movement of Mental Revolution with the scope of activities of the Independent Movement. Assistance in packaging workshops for souvenirs, workshop and promotion assistance, tree planting activities and meetings for the preparation of outputs and final reports. The method implemented is to record citizens who will participate in this activity, and provide explanations related to the National Movement of Mental Revolution program with the community. Assisting packaging workshops for souvenirs related to product packaging and product branding so that they can be marketed and used as distinctive souvenirs. Carrying out business formation and promotion workshop assistance , aimed at increasing the promotion of village product innovation. Carrying out tree planting activities, the tree seeds planted are a composition of traditional herbs. The expected output of this activity is that the economy of the village community continues to grow by continuing to innovate through herbal products.

Keywords: Traditional Herbs; Village Oil; Empowering Business Actors

INTRODUCTION

Many villagers make traditional medicines, namely making traditional oils and herbs. Data in the field found that these traditional medicines were made based on family needs or requests from relatives or friends. There is great potential in utilizing this traditional medicine as a small and medium enterprise in self-reliant community economy. Small and medium enterprises are businesses that can provide the widest possible employment opportunities for the community, so as to accelerate equity and increase people's income and be able to improve

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the economy in realizing national stability in general and economic stability in particular (Djabbar & Sudirman, 2017).

Village oil and traditional herbs are one of the cultural products that have been passed down both in the way of production and recipes to treat health problems such as wounds, fractures, fever, itching, maternal health and other diseases such as helping to treat colds, lumbago, rheumatism, sprains and can strengthen bones in infants (Winarno, F.G, 2021). The importance of traditional medicines for the Karo people themselves can be seen from their use in everyday life. Village people usually keep several types of traditional medicines at home in anticipation of help when sick. Villagers strongly believe that traditional medicine can maintain health, increase endurance and cure several types of diseases. Village oil and traditional oukup herbs are not only used by the community, but by people in the city, because it is considered very efficacious benefits used by the community in carrying out health care.

The high demand for village oil products and traditional herbs makes people produce them for family use and also to be commercialized in increasing income. However, in the implementation of commercialization of village oil and traditional herbs, several problems are as follows: The demand for village oil products and traditional herbs is only once without any demand again due to fluctuating production prices and less variety of product packaging; The production process is only carried out if there is demand, making production costs expensive and high product prices. Kotler and Armstrong explained that marketing strategy in business units is a process that is highly prioritized so that it can achieve its goals in marketing (Abdurrahman, 2015). Seeing the problems experienced by the village community, the innovative solution of village entrepreneurship, as an effort to lift the potential of the village through mentoring programs for small business actors and village cooperatives so that they can be economically independent. In carrying out economic development, all levels of society and government must be involved in taking regional development initiatives through all resource support in designing regional economic development (Pujiono, 2013). Network development is also carried out as an effort to collaborate with other organizations, individuals or groups, so that together they support each other to achieve goals (Firmansyah, 2022), then activities to increase village economic independence through assistance in innovative products of traditional oukup herbs and village oil include: Preparatory meetings; Tree planting which is the composition in the making of traditional herbs and village oils; Assistance in Packaging Workshop for Typical Souvenirs; Assistance in MSME Formation and Promotion Workshops; Relevance to the Main Theme, namely Firm Determination, Rise for the Country With this village entrepreneurial activity, it can form a village-based innovation ecosystem and transmit it to other villages in the community to rise to advance the country's economy. Providing attractive and informative packaging and labeling can be an attraction for customers and can

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increase the selling price of products, because the products sold must meet customer satisfaction (Dzakiya, 2021). The village's entrepreneurial activities are the scope of activities in supporting the Independent Movement. The objectives of this activity are as follows: Providing benefits to the community for entrepreneurship while preserving and promoting the traditional cultural heritage of the ancestors; Building collaboration between the Government and Village Communities in supporting the improvement of economic independence so that employment opportunities in the Village are open; Provide experience and teaching to students so that they have the ability to serve the community, have a work ethic and insight in increasing the economic independence of the community through entrepreneurial activities and product innovation in preparing students to enter the world of work.

RESEARCH ELABORATIONS

The National Movement of Mental Revolution program with the community has been carried out with the theme "Increasing Village Economic Independence through Assistance in Innovation of Traditional Ingredients and Village Oil Products". provide an explanation regarding the program of the National Movement for Mental Revolution with the community which will be carried out for the next two months. Meetings function as a medium for a group of people to align ideas in implementing certain activity programs (Achmad Behori and Badrul Alamin, 2018). The next activity in the program is mentoring packaging workshops for typical souvenirs. then carried out mentoring workshops on business formation and promotion, aimed at increasing the promotion of village innovation products. Micro enterprises are economically productive businesses, so marketing is a very important aspect (Ismawati, Yuniastri, 2021) The next activity is planting, carried out in the Village. The tree seeds planted are a composition of traditional herbs and village oils.

The implementation of the program with the community consists of the following series of activities: Activity Preparation Meeting; Assistance in packaging workshops for cendramata; Assistance in MSME Formation and Promotion Workshops; Tree Planting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The program of the National Movement for Mental Revolution with the community begins with the preparation of activities. The program steps that have been carried out are: Conducting activity preparation meetings. Preparatory meetings have been conducted by the proposer team of the National Movement for Mental Revolution program. Based on the results

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of the meeting, the community fully supports the National Mental Revolution Movement program which aims to foster the creative skills of village residents, so it is hoped that the program will be able to increase the village's economic independence through assistance in the innovation of traditional herb products and village oil.

With the initial preparation meeting, it makes it easier for the team to carry out sustainable activities in the village. The next activity is: Packaging Workshop Assistance for typical souvenirs. This activity aims to improve the packaging skills of karo oil and traditional oukup herbs in villagers which later these innovative products can become typical souvenirs. Tarimana (2017) found that packaging, labeling and product quality significantly affect purchasing decisions. Assistance in MSME formation workshops and Promotion.. This activity aims to improve marketing skills in marketing innovative products and provide entrepreneurial spirit to rural communities so that the business carried out can develop to reach the national and even international level.

Tree planting activities. Tree planting is carried out in villages that participate in planting tree seedlings which are a composition of traditional herbs and village oil. The seeds planted include good seedlings so that they support the success of growing seedlings in tree planting (Nizar et al. 2019) as well as tree seedlings planted in the village. This will increase the value of impactful products with more trees that can be used as traditional medicine and village oil.

CONCLUSIONS

With this activity, it can promote traditional herbs and oils for health so that they have economic product value for village communities. Traditional herbs and village oils have been proven to improve economic welfare for community members. In addition to greening the environment, this tahaman can be cultivated with the end result for traditional herbs and healthy village oils.

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